

EFFECT OF PEER FEEDBACK TECHNIQUE IN TEACHING WRITING ON STUDENTS' WRITING ACHIEVEMENT OF WRITING II COURSE AT ENGLISH DEPARTMENT FKIP LAMBUNG MANGKURAT UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: Providing student with clear feedback is one of the ways that can facilitate students to be able to write well. This study is aimed to find out the difference between students who are taught by using peer feedback and those who are taught by using teacher feedback. This was an experimental research that used quantitative approach. The subjects of this research were students of Writing II of English Department of FKIP Lambung Mangkurat University. Writing II class A1 was the experiment group and Writing II class A2 was the control group. The data of this research were students' writing achievement in both experiment and control class. The data analyzed by using SPSS (One-Way ANOVA). Ha was found 0.003 which meant that Ha was accepted. It showed that there was difference in students' writing achievement between students in experiment and control class. It was proved that students who were taught by using peer feedback had higher achievement in writing than students who were taught by using teacher feedback. On the whole, it is suggested for students to improve their ability in proof reading and for the teachers, it is suggested to apply not only teacher feedback technique, but also peer feedback technique to their students in writing class.

Keywords: writing, peer feedback, teacher feedback

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INTRODUCTION

Writing in English which is not students' native language is very demanding for them. First problem is how to generate the ideas. When they have got their ideas, they have to think about those ideas in English. After getting the ideas, they have to make one idea related to others in order to make the writing have smooth organization. Another problem is that they need to deal with the use of vocabulary and spelling which are totally different from Bahasa Indonesia as their native language and grammar which has different pattern from Bahasa Indonesia.

Providing student with clear feedback is one of the ways that can facilitate students able to learn their errors and fix them. The aim of feedback is to bring about self-awareness and improvement. Feedback defines as information for the learner about his or her performance of a learning task, usually with the objective of improving this performance (Van Gennip et al., 2009 as cited in Ahmadian et al., 2013).

Giving feedback does not mean hunting students' errors (Muth'im, 2016). Giving feedback means telling students about the progress they are making as well as guiding them to areas for improvement. Feedback provides information for teachers and students. Feedback gives teachers information about individual and collective class progress and it also a form of evaluation on their own teaching. For students, feedback is an ongoing form of assessment which is more focused than marks or grades. Feedback is also one of forms of motivation that can encourage students to study and to use language to the best of their ability (Lewis, 2002).

In the process of writing, there are some forms of giving feedback including peer feedback, teacher feedback, self-assessment, teacher assessment and so forth (Nation, 2009).

When students have got feedback from others, it is expected that they have chance to fix some errors in their writing. After fixing the errors, students will collect the revision to their teachers. What teachers need to see is the improvement that their students made because feedback is given for the sake of students' learning, not for the sake of finding errors and then ignoring the students (Muth'im, 2016).

Some research show different results about the effect of some feedbacks. Connor and Asenavage (1994, as cited in Miao et al., 2006) investigate the impact of peer and teacher feedback on eight English as Second Language (ESL) students from different countries in a university in the United States. They found that teacher feedback had much more significant effect than peer feedback, with only 5% of peer feedback resulting in changes. On the other hand, Villamil and De Guerrero (1998, as cited in Miao, Badger, and Zhen, 2006) find that peer feedback had a beneficial effect on the quality of writing and also led to more learner autonomy, though they made no comparison with teacher feedback. According to Chin Lin and Chieh Chien (2009), most participants addressed peer correction activities did make them learning experience more relaxing, confident, and inspiring. It happens because they do not feel intimidated when they get feedback from their friends since it is communication between friends, someone who is in the same age with them.

The varied results from some research had taken the researcher attention to conduct the research on this area. Furthermore, the researcher is interested in conducting a research entitled "The Effect of Peer Feedback Technique in Teaching Writing on Students' Writing Achievement of Writing II Course at English Department FKIP Lambung Mangkurat University Academic Year 2016/2017".

In order to give clear feedback to the students, the researcher uses feedback sheet that contains all components in writing that should be concerned by the teacher and student. The researcher chooses Writing II students at English Department FKIP Lambung Mangkurat University as the subjects of this research. The consideration is that Writing II students have passed Writing I where students have already got prior knowledge about components in writing a paragraph, unity and coherence in writing a paragraph, and the way to generate topic sentences in a paragraph and they have passed Structure I where they have already learnt some tenses and other grammatical rules.

Based on the theory, phenomenon, and also the observation from the researcher, it can be described that the problem of this research is: "Is there any difference in students' writing achievement between students who are taught by using peer feedback and those who are taught by using teacher feedback?" Furthermore, the objective of this research is to find out whether there is difference in students' writing achievement between those who are taught by using peer feedback and those who are taught by using teacher feedback.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The approach of this research is quantitative approach. According to Fraenkel and Wallen (2012:275) quasi experimental includes experimental group and control group on a certain variable. The quasi-experimental research means the classes are manipulated to receive the treatment. There are some steps in order to do this research. They are preparation, execution, and analysis. In conducting this research, the researcher prepared some attachment to conduct the research. They are syllabus of Writing II, Rencana Kegiatan Pembelajaran Mingguan (RKPM) which was the instruction guide about teaching and learning process in the classroom, and feedback sheet in order to provide the students and the lecturer to give feedback in the classroom. The feedback sheet contained five components of writing; content, organization, language use, vocabulary, and mechanics to be analyzed by the feedback giver. In order to make everything run well, the researcher also

decided some topics that students had in every meeting. There were some procedures that the researcher did in conducting this research. They are pre-test and treatment. In doing pre-test, the researcher asked the subjects in both experimental and control group to write a paragraph about a topic that she gave to them. In doing treatment for experimental group, there were some steps; explaining the codes that were used in giving feedback, giving model on how to do peer feedback, and giving revisions based on the feedback.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

FINDING

After the researcher had tested that the test was valid and reliable, the researcher conducted the test. It was started by conducting pre-test in both experiment and control class. The result of conducting pre-test was to make sure that the students from both experiment and control class were homogeneous. The pretest average score of experiment was 75 and the pre-test average score of control class was 76. The result proved that students in both experiment and control class were homogeneous. Next, it was presented the result of the data in experiment class from both raters.

TABLE 4. 3

Students	First Rater		Second Rater	
	Pretest	Posttest	Pretest	Posttest
Sample 1	82	86	81	89
Sample 2	68	84	65	85
STUDENTS' AVERAGE SCORE	75	78.5	74	78.6

The Result of Experiment Class

The result of the pre-test and posttest of the students in experiment class in Writing II class A1 was presented in Table 4.6. The sample 1 was the sample of the subject who got the highest score in posttest. The sample 2 was the sample of the subject who got the lowest score in pretest. The whole data of experiment class can be seen on the appendix.

The average pretest score of the students in experiment class was 75 from the first rater and 74 from the second rater. Moreover, the average post-test score of the students in experiment class was 78.5 from the first rater and 78.6 from the second rater.

FIGURE 4. 1

The Result of Experiment Class

The Result of the Test in Control Class

TABLE 4. 4
The Result of Control Class

Students	First Rater		Second Rater	
	Pretest	Posttest	Pretest	Posttest
Sample 1	66	61	69	69
Sample 2	83	85	81	83
STUDENTS' AVERAGE SCORE	76	73	76	74

The result of the pre-test and posttest of the students in control class in Writing II class A1 as control class was presented in Table 4.4. The sample 1 was the lowest score in pretest. The first rater gave 66 and the second rater gave 69. The sample 2 was the highest score in posttest. The first rater gave 85 and the second rater gave 83. The whole data of experiment class can be seen on the appendix.

The scores in pretest in control class did not always increase in posttest. There was fluctuation in the scores. The average of students' score in control class from both first and second rater in the pretest was 76. The average score in posttest decreased. The average score of posttest from the first rater was 73, and the average score of posttest from the second rater was 74. The result of control class could also be seen on Figure 4.2.

FIGURE 4. 2

The Result of Control Class Hypothesis Testing

In order to test hypothesis of the research, first step was to find out the average scores of posttest scores from two raters in both experiment and control class. Next step is completing three kinds of testing before testing the hypothesis. The first test was testing the normality of the test. From Table 4.5, it could be seen that the data of this research were normal, since the point was more than 0.05.

Normality Testing

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

- Test distribution is Normal.
- Calculated from data.

The second test was homogeneity testing. It was to test the homogeneous of the data. From Table 4.6, it could be concluded that the data of this research were homogeneous, since the significant (sig. point) was more than 0.05.

DISCUSSION

Based on the research finding, it was proved that students in experiment class which were taught by using peer feedback have higher achievement in writing than students in control class which were taught by using teacher feedback. This finding means that there was different result of those two kinds of feedback when they were applied to the students. When students got feedback from their friends, they could make higher score in their writing.

This research has similar results to the result of Villamil and De Guerrero's research (1998, as cited in Miao, Badger, and Zhen, 2006) that find that peer feedback has a beneficial effect on the quality of writing. This is also supported by the results from Paulus (1999, as cited in Hyland, 2006) and Mendonca and Johnson (1994, as cited in Hyland, 2006). Those results say that peer feedback influence student revision significantly and students used their peers' comments in more than half their revisions. The effect of peer feedback in another EFL (English as Foreign Language) country has also had same result. It is said that peer feedback on Iranian EFL learners' writing ability gives more effect and it has possible superiority over teacher feedback. One factor highlighted in the research studies is the importance of training. The students were trained on how to give feedback to their peers and how to respond the feedback from their peers before they gave feedback from their peers.

Yet, some theories argue that peer feedback is more successful than teacher feedback. Connor and Asenavage (1994, as cited in Miao *et al.*, 2006) investigate that teacher feedback has a much more significant effect than peer feedback, with only 5% of peer feedback resulting in changes. This result was supported by Hyland (2003) that says that many students see their teacher's feedback as crucial to their improvement as writers.

However, in this research, the applying of teacher feedback in control class spent much more time than the applying of peer feedback. Teacher could not give the feedback directly in one meeting since she had to read students' writings, which were more than 20 pieces of paper and then write down the feedback in feedback sheet. This phenomenon was supported by Hyland (2003) that states that peer feedback can activate learner participation in the classroom and it also reduces teachers' workload since they do not give the feedback, but they only act as the observer.

This research proposed peer feedback as a technique in teaching writing where the students have chance to read and analyze their friends' writing as well as receiving the feedback from their friends that they can easily understand. As Chin Lin and Chieh Chien (2009) mention that students do not feel intimidated when they get feedback from their friends since it is communication between friends, someone who is in the same age with them. The use of peer feedback in students' writing activity has made students encourage their own autonomy. It makes students able to identify errors from their students writing and it makes students aware and more careful to write down their own writing. As stated by Miao, Badger, and Zhen (2006), peer feedback does lead to improvements and appears to encourage student autonomy.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Conclusion

Based on the research findings and discussion, it was found out that the level of significance in testing the hypothesis of this research was 0.0003, which means that there was difference in students' writing achievement between students who were taught by using peer feedback, and those who were taught by using teacher feedback. It can be concluded that teaching writing by using peer feedback technique might be good for

students, since the effect of using peer feedback technique has been proven good for increasing students' writing achievement.

Furthermore, the difference result between teaching writing by using peer feedback and teacher feedback might be because of the following: (a) there was training before students were asked to give feedback to their friends. In the training, students was also shown how to fill in the feedback sheet and how to respond it, (b) students directly got feedback sheet from their peers, while the control group who got feedback from teacher should wait for a week to get their feedback, (c) students do not feel intimidated when they get feedback from their friends since it is communication between friends, someone who is in the same age with them. Although the communication was through a piece of paper, in this case is feedback sheet, the students feel more comfortable to read and revise their writing from their friends' feedback, and (d) the idea of giving feedback to their friends has made students encourage their autonomy. It makes them aware to common mistakes that they probably will make in writing.

Suggestion

Based on finding, some suggestions are recommended. First, for the students, it is suggested to improve their ability in proof reading so that every time they write, they will also read before submitting their writing to the teacher. Because when they read, they will see what they cannot see when they only write. Second, for the teachers, it is suggested to apply not only teacher feedback technique, but also peer feedback technique to their students in writing class. It is not only for increasing students' achievement in writing, but also for decreasing teachers' workload. It is also suggested to apply other kinds of media in doing peer feedback, such as work group. It can increase students' participation in the classroom. Third, for future researcher, it is suggested to conduct a descriptive study about students' revision in peer feedback, or to conduct a descriptive study about what factors that make students accept more on their friends' feedback than on their teacher feedback, some interview or observation might be better for additional instrument.

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